

This is the final, pre-publication draft of the paper. To cite this article: Cristian Iftode, Alexandra Zorila & Anda Zahiu (2024) Love Drugs and the Authenticity Charge: Why Narrative Templates Matter, AJOB Neuroscience, 15:4, 246-248, DOI: 10.1080/21507740.2024.2402223

Love Drugs and the Authenticity Charge: Why Narrative Templates Matter

Cristian Iftode, Alexandra Zorila & Anda Zahiu

Abstract: The study conducted by Lantian et al. is a timely investigation into the potential sources of moral resistance to the biomedical enhancement of romantic relationships through the use of love drugs. Results point to perceived authenticity as the main catalyst of relative moral disapproval. Nevertheless, the authors largely neglect the impact of narrative templates on the attribution of authenticity (Iftode et al. 2022; Iftode et al. 2023). We argue that the difference in perceived authenticity between the use of love drugs and more traditional means of rekindling romantic feelings could be potentially smaller if one were to deploy concepts pertaining to the relational narrative view of identity in constructing vignettes. The appeal to love drugs can be integrated into a narrative template that allows for this episode to become an integral and meaningful part of one's love and life story. We imagine a series of vignettes that could illustrate this point and open up research avenues in this direction.

Keywords: authenticity, love drugs, identity, human enhancement.

The study conducted by Lantian et al. (2024) investigates the potential sources of moral resistance to the biomedical enhancement of romantic relationships through the use of love drugs, drawing on previous work by Earp and Savulescu (2020). The results point to the perceived inauthenticity of resulting emotions and mental states as the main catalyst of moral disapproval among participants, compared to other means of rekindling the romantic flame. However, both the study at hand and seminal work on this topic fail to address the critical importance of integrating the use of biomedical love enhancers into a personal and couple narrative. We argue that the narrative account of identity, which employs the concept of narrative templates to enable individuals to make sense of their lives and decisions, can better account for fluctuations in how we evaluate the authenticity of mental states in different contexts. Secondly, we suggest a means of integrating these insights into future experimental studies.

Narrative templates: how to make sense of love drugs

The narrative identity account does not impose the high standards of ‘polished literary texts’ on self-narratives, as critics have wrongly suggested (see Postan 2022, 71). Instead, it acknowledges the more or less conscious use of narrative tools for selecting and interpreting an individual’s life experiences whenever they reflect on who they are, their reasons for acting in a particular manner, or their judgments about the world and other people. One type of tool we use daily is narrative *templates*, which help us make sense of new experiences and explain significant life decisions. Narrative templates can be understood as shared frameworks of meaning within a community that are meant to inform individuals about what to expect, how to behave, and what the likely outcomes are in culturally significant situations.

A self-narrative functions not only as a means to develop and enact one’s identity but also as the general framework or ‘lens’ through which an individual sees and interprets the world (Schechtman 1996; 2014). Therefore, the narrative account retains an undeniable practical as well as normative dimension. It doesn’t refer to a solitary pursuit but to a collaborative endeavor with one’s significant others (Iftode et al. 2022). As with personal autonomy, we are also justified in addressing the relational dimension of narrative identity and authenticity (Leuenberger 2020; Zorilă 2023; Iftode et al. 2023).

Towards the end of their paper, Lantian and colleagues cite the argument from equivalence advanced by Earp and Savulescu (2020), which posits that there is no fundamental difference between traditional methods of rekindling love in a long-term relationship (such as going on romantic vacations), psychological therapy, and the use of love drugs, as long as a person believes “it is okay to work on love” (Earp and Savulescu 2020, 11). However, laypeople seem unconvinced by this argument, and the authors of the paper acknowledge that “further research will be needed to precisely understand what makes romantic feelings elicited by psychological therapy and love drugs less ‘authentic’ than those elicited by more ordinary methods” (Lantian et al. 2024, 12).

In our view, people will tend to resist the use of love drugs, or at least judge them as an artificial and thus questionable means of preserving a relationship, as long as their use remains unintegrated into *a culturally accepted narrative template*. Such a template would allow for the administration of love drugs to become an intelligible and meaningful episode in the love story that is incorporated into the self-narrative of each partner and into the couple’s shared narrative. Iftode and colleagues have previously argued that people’s resistance to some new

medical technologies can be explained by the lack of a ‘template of meaning’ or a ‘narrative pattern’ based on ‘cultural archetypes.’ They also noted that the reluctance towards enhancement interventions is related to the fact that transformative experiences of this kind are often “entrapped in devalued, even dystopian scenarios” in our society (Iftode et al. 2022, 14-15). We believe that this explanation applies well to the case of love drugs.

Another way to put it is that resorting to a love drug without a narrative template to support the decision fails to satisfy what Schechtman (1996) calls ‘the articulation constraint’ for self-narratives. This constraint requires individuals to be able to explain the connections between their various decisions and life episodes, all constituent parts of their self-narratives, in an intelligible manner to themselves and to others. Using a love drug without such a template of meaning would seem like inserting a foreign element into a first-person configured narrative – the use of a substance that affects the neurochemistry of a brain that is no longer ‘in love.’ This element counts as a causal, impersonal explanation of a person’s change in mood, thus fitting into a third-person redescription of a love story using scientific, neurochemical notions.

Drawing upon narratives: a suggestion for future studies

Within psychological science, studies often involve participants recounting detailed stories about specific events or important moments in their lives. The narrative accounts are then analyzed by coding them and examining their dimensions and features. In this context, conducting interviews that allow individuals to elaborate on and provide details about their experiences seems to be the best way to identify underlying self-narratives.

Nevertheless, our argument about the importance of narrative templates can also be tentatively translated into quantitative studies that make use of vignette evaluation. Specifically, we suggest that the research under discussion could benefit from the introduction of a third study that requires participants to evaluate the same potential mediators (perceived authenticity, intensity, expected durability of love) for two different ways of framing one of the main independent variables (the use of love drugs). The pre-study questionnaire can be designed to roughly identify participants’ core beliefs and values. This information will later be used to determine if there are significant correlations between the scenarios they choose and the narrative templates they seem to employ. Scenario A and scenario A’ would each be presented to the target and control groups, respectively, while retaining the other two main independent variables from Study 2 conducted by Lantian and colleagues for both groups:

- (A) Paul and Sophie both use a chemical substance known to boost romantic feelings towards one's partner.
- (A') Paul and Sophie both engage in the 'Eleusinian ritual of love.' They go to Greece and, at dawn, they dress in white clothes and symbolically renew their vows in the presence of a love priestess. The culminating point of the ritual is when they share a cup of wine mixed with a chemical substance known to boost romantic feelings towards one's partner.
- (B) Paul and Sophie go to psychological therapy.
- (C) Paul and Sophie plan for and spend more time together.

The variation in the love drug condition (A and A') can shed light on the effect that narrative templates have in modulating laypeople's perception of the same event (imbibing a love drug). We hypothesize that scores for A' will reveal greater acceptability compared to scores for A.

Future studies should seek to eliminate two confounding factors that could potentially be present in the original studies conducted by Lantian and colleagues. The first one is the possibility of deceit toward the other member of the couple. The second concern is that the vignettes used in Study 2 conjoin a doctor's general recommendation for a method of intervention with its later confirmed success. This conjunction suggests that all methods are interchangeable, as they render the same results. A clear indication that a doctor would tailor interventions to a patient's specific context, preferences, and values might be useful in avoiding a one-size-fits-all approach, while also suggesting that patients do not regard said intervention as a loose end in their broader life narrative.

FUNDING

The authors acknowledge being funded by the European Commission Horizon WIDERA under Grant Agreement No. 101131683 (CHANGER Project), and by the European Union (ERC, avataResponsibility, 101117761). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

REFERENCES

- Earp, B. D., and J. Savulescu. 2020. Psychedelic relationship enhancement: Précis of *Love Drugs*. *Philosophy and Public Issues* 10(3): 3–28. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Brian-Earp-2/publication/344875872_Psychedelic_Relationship_Enhancement/links/6048ea8d299bf1f5d83d6bd3/Psychedelic-Relationship-Enhancement.pdf.
- Iftode, C., A. Zorila, C. Vica, and E. Mihailov. 2022. Experimental and relational authenticity: How neurotechnologies impact narrative identities. *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences* 2022: 1–8. doi:10.1007/s11097-022-09825-7.
- Iftode, C., A. Zorila, C. Vica, and M. Leuenberger. 2023. ‘Living a life of our own’: Why authenticity is more than a condition for autonomy. *The Journal of Value Inquiry* 2023: 1–26. doi:10.1007/s10790-023-09967-0.
- Lantian, A., J. Boudesseul, and F. Cova. 2024. Prescription for Love: An Experimental Investigation of Laypeople’s Relative Moral Disapproval of Love Drugs 2024: 1–16. *AJOB Neuroscience*. doi:10.1080/21507740.2024.2326923.
- Leuenberger, M. 2020. In defense of narrative authenticity: Response to the discussion of Pugh et al. and Nyholm and O’Neill. *Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics*, 29, 656–667. doi:10.1017/S0963180120000407.
- Postan, E. 2022. *Embodied narratives: Protecting identity interests through ethical governance of bioinformation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Schechtman, M. 1996. *The constitution of selves*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Schechtman, M. 2014. *Staying alive: Personal identity, practical concerns, and the unity of a life*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Zorila, A. 2023. Neurotechnologies and identity changes: What the narrative view can add to the story. *AJOB Neuroscience* 14(1): 48–50. doi:10.1080/21507740.2022.2150713.